

Synthesis and application of Alizarin red S bonded polyurethane foam for separation and preconcentration of trace amounts of some metal ions in wastewater

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A stable chelating resin matrix was prepared by covalently linking Alizarin red S with polyurethane foam, through a -N=N- group, and identified through UV/Vis and IR. The resin was used in batch and column techniques for the separation and preconcentration of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} from wastewater. The various parameters affecting the retention efficiency of the tested metal ions from aqueous media by the Alizarin red S bonded polyurethane foam (Al-Puf) were examined, e.g. pH, contact time, sorption isotherm, flow rate and breakthrough capacity. Extraction was accomplished during 5–15 min at pH 9, 2–4 and 4–6 for Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II}, respectively. The capacities of Al-Puf were 4.2, 2.5 and 2.4 mmol/g for Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II}, respectively. The detection limit was about 4 ng/ml for preconcentration factor of 50 has been achieved (rsd ~ 3.46%). The kinetics and thermodynamics of the sorption of the tested ions onto Al-Puf have been studied. The sorption of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} onto Al-Puf follow a first order rate equation, with the rate constant, *k*, to be 0.211, 0.448 and 0.207 min⁻¹, respectively. The values of Gibbs free energy (ΔG) for the sorption of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} were -4.29, -2.73 and -3.43 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively at 298 K. The proposed method has been successfully applied to the assay of tested metal ions in waste water.

The recovery of silver(I), mercury(II) and lead(III) from industrial wastewater becomes more important due to the rapidly growing demand for them in different industrial and also to increasing concerns about global environmental pollution. Mercury and lead are hazardous and poisonous for humans, plants and animals^{1,2}. The low level of these elements in environmental and biological samples makes it necessary to preconcentrate these samples before their actual determination. A number of solid/liquid preconcentration systems have been used for metal ions in off-line procedures such as ion exchangers and chelating resins^{3–12}.

Polyurethane foam has been used as a sorbent to separate and preconcentrate has a wide variety of inorganic and organic species from different media by conventional methods. Braun¹³ published some reviews about the use of polyurethane foam in separation and preconcentration procedures applied to several systems of analytical interest. Polyurethane foam can be used without pretreatment (unloaded foam) and also reagent immobilization (loaded foam)^{13–30}. Two main problems necessitate the need for preparation of foams in which organic reagents or functional groups are chemically bonded : lack of selectivity of unloaded foams and leaching of reagents from loaded ones. The two

methodologies are frequently adopted for such designing. The first involves sorption of chelating ligands onto a matrix^{31,32} and the other is based on covalent coupling of a ligand with a polymer backbone through a spacer arm, generally -N=N- group.

In the present paper the synthesis of a new chelating resin, for the incorporation of Alizarin red S into polyurethane foam matrix. This method is based on covalent coupling of the Alizarin red S with a polymer backbone through a -N=N- group. Alizarin red S bonded polyurethane foam was characterized through UV/Vis and IR spectra, density, and resistant toward different solvents. The analytical applicability of Al-Puf as chelating resin was tested for the collection of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} from wastewater.

Results and discussion

Characterization of Alizarin red S bonded polyurethane foam (Al-Puf) :

Density : The densities of the white foam and of the Al-Puf are measured. The values obtained are 20, 60 kg/m³ respectively. These values indicate that the Al-Puf has more crosslinkage than the white foam, which may be due to additional bonds between the reagent and 1° amino groups in the polyurethane foam.

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UV/Vis and IR spectra : UV/Vis spectral studies on white foam and Al-Puf, the dry foam (2.5 × 0.8 × 0.2 cm) are placed in the cell, which was filled with benzene. IR spectrum was recorded using potassium bromide technique. Due to the high number of bands in white foam in UV and IR spectra, it is difficult to identify the characteristic groups of Al-Puf. But the difference can be summarized for the band of the reagent appearing at 480 nm. Then the shift in the broadband absorption of -OH and -NH groups from 3354.4 to 3381.4 cm⁻¹, and the azo group appeared at 1602.1 cm⁻¹ for IR spectra.

Effect of solvents on washing out Alizarin red S from Al-Puf : In order to study the leaching of Alizarin red S from Al-Puf with different solvents using batch mode, 0.2 g of reagent foam cubes are mixed with 25 ml of the solvent and shaken for 30 min. The reagent leached by the solvent was measured. The reagent was not detected in the solution. The resin shows a good chemical stability in the presence of 1–6 M HCl, 1–5 M H₂SO₄, 1–5 M NaOH, acetone, methanol, ethanol, acetonitrile and tetrahydrofuran. The expected Alizarin red S bonded polyurethane foam has formula :

Preconcentration and separation of Ag^I, Pb^{II} and Hg^{II} :

Effect of the pH on the sorption of metal ions : The effect of the pH on the extraction of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} using Al-Puf was examined. The percentage extraction of these metal ions by Al-Puf was plotted against the pH value (Fig. 1). It was noted from these curves that the Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} were separated from the aqueous solution having pH values, 9, 2–4 and 4–6 respectively. The distribution coef-

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on sorption of metal ions onto Alizarin red S bonded polyurethane foam : (◆) Ag^I, (■) Hg^{II}, (▲) Pb^{II}.

ficients (K_d) values and separation factor (α) of the tested metal ions were summarized in Table 1 which show that the selectivity sequence at pH 2 was in order Hg^{II} > Ag^I > Pb^{II}, between pH 4 and 6 Pb^{II} > Hg^{II} > Ag^I while at pH 9, the selectivity adsorbed of Ag^I > Hg^{II} > Pb^{II}. These results show that ruling of the pH may enhance the selectivity of the tested metal ion separation with Al-Puf.

Kinetic study : The rate of extraction of tested metal ions onto Al-Puf was measured by the batch technique. The results obtained were presented in Fig. 2. The time required for the sorption equilibrium of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} ions was found to be 10, 5 and 20 min respectively. The kinetic data of the sorption of tested metal ions onto Al-Puf was calculated according to first order reaction (Lagergren equation) :

$$\log (Q_e - Q_t) = \log Q_e - \frac{k_1 t}{2.303} \quad (1)$$

where Q_e and Q_t are the amount of metal ions sorbed at equilibrium and at time t . k_1 is the rate constant of the sorption. A plot of $\log (Q_e - Q_t)$ vs t shows a straight line, which indicates that the process is a first order reaction with respect to the adsorbed concentration of each metal ion. The

Table 1. Effect of pH on distribution coefficient factor (K_d) and separation factor (α) of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II}

pH	Distribution coefficient (K_d)			$\alpha_{Ag^I/Hg^{II}}$	$\alpha_{Pb^{II}/Hg^{II}}$	α_{Pb^{II}/Ag^I}
	Ag ^I	Hg ^{II}	Pb ^{II}			
2	187.5	375	125	0.50	0.33	0.67
4	187.5	375	500	0.50	1.33	2.67
6	291.6	321.4	500	0.91	1.56	1.71
8	375, 708*	291.7	152.5	1.29, 2.43*	0.52	0.40
10	269.5	265.6	152.5	2.14	0.57	0.27
12	375	187.5	140.9	2	0.75	0.35

* at pH : 9

Table 2. Kinetic and thermodynamic parameters for sorption of metal ions onto Al-Puf at room temperature

Metal ions	K_c	ΔE kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG kJ mol ⁻¹	k_1 min ⁻¹	k_{-1} min ⁻¹	k' min ⁻¹	$t_{1/2}$ min
Ag ^I	5.66	9.43	-4.287	0.211	0.037	0.248	3.28
Hg ^{II}	3.01	8.33	-2.725	0.448	0.149	0.597	1.55
Pb ^{II}	4.00	9.90	-3.429	0.207	0.052	0.259	3.35

Fig. 2. Rate of sorption of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} onto Al-Puf : (◆) Ag^I, (■) Hg^{II}, (▲) Pb^{II}.

rate constant calculated from the slope for the sorption of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} are 0.211, 0.448 and 0.207 min⁻¹, respectively. Then the half-life of sorption, rate constant of desorption and the overall rate constant can be calculated. ($t_{1/2} = 0.693/k_1$, $k_{-1} = k_1/K_c$, $k' = k_1 + k_{-1}$). The values of $t_{1/2}$, k_{-1} and k' are summarized in Table 2. This rapid extraction was due to the application of the batch technique, which was relatively fast and efficient as compared to the other resins.

Sorption isotherm : The uptake of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} onto Al-Puf was determined as a function of metal ion concentration in the aqueous solution. The isotherms show good linear relationship over relatively wide range of elements concentrations (Fig. 3). The capacity of one gram of Al-Puf for the sorption of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} calculated from the isotherm curves found to be 3.14 and 1.75 and 1.5-mmol g⁻¹, respectively. The results of the tested metal ions sorbed onto Al-Puf were analyzed in terms of Freundlich ($\log Q_c = \log K_f + \frac{1}{n} \log Q_e$) equation. Where Q_c is the amount of metal ions sorbed per unit mass of the Al-Puf, Q_e is the amount of metal ions adsorbed at equilibrium. K_f and n , are constants. The numerical values of adsorption capacity (K_f) for Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} were 7.24×10^{-4} , 5.25×10^{-4} and 3.02×10^{-4} mol g⁻¹ respectively. While $1/n$ indicating the energy and intensity were 0.93, 1.09 and 1.12 respectively. The

numerical value of $0 < 1/n < 1$ indicates that sorption capacity is only slightly reduced at lower equilibrium concentrations in the sorption of Ag^I. For testing the curve fit

of the Langmuir model ($\frac{Q_c}{Q_e} = \frac{1}{K_L b} + \frac{Q_c}{K_L}$) to experimental data involve plotting of Q_e/Q_c against Q_e . Where the value of K_L is constant corresponding to the monolayer coverage, while the sorption coefficient (b) is constant related to the enthalpy. The values of K_L were 2.8×10^{-3} and 1.2×10^{-3} mol g⁻¹, while the values of parameter (b) were 5.9×10^2 and 6.8×10^2 dm³ mol⁻¹ for Ag^I and Pb^{II} respectively. The plot of Q_e/Q_c vs Q_e of the experimental data for the sorbed of Hg^{II} onto Al-Puf gives horizontal line. The Dubinin-Radushkevich isotherm model ($\ln Q_c = \ln K_{D-R} - \beta \epsilon^2$) was tested with the experimental data to describe the

Fig. 3. Extraction isotherms of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} from aqueous solution using Al-Puf : (◆) Ag^I, (■) Hg^{II}, (▲) Pb^{II}.

sorption equilibrium. Where Q_c is the amount of metal ions sorbed per unit mass of Al-Puf, K_{D-R} is the maximum amount of metal ions adsorbed, β is constant with dimen-

sions of energy and Polanyi $\epsilon = RT \ln \left(1 + \frac{1}{q_e} \right)$ where R is a gas constant in kJ K⁻¹ mol⁻¹, and T is a temperature in Kelvin. The plot of $\ln Q_c$ vs ϵ^2 is a straight line. The values of β for sorption of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} from the slope are -5.64×10^{-3} , -5.13×10^{-3} and -7.27×10^{-3} kJ² mol⁻²,

respectively. In addition, the calculated sorption activation energy (E) values ($E = 1/\sqrt{-2\beta}$) are to be 9.43, 8.33 and 9.9 kJ mol⁻¹ for Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} ions respectively, which reflects that the rate of sorption is relatively fast. Also, the Gibbs free energy was calculated from the following equation :

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_c \quad (2)$$

where ΔG and K_c are Gibbs free energy and equilibrium constant. The values of ΔG for the sorption of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} are -4.29, -2.73 and -3.43 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. The negative value of ΔG may be due to the spontaneous nature of sorption.

Breakthrough capacity : Breakthrough capacity was defined as the amount of the metal ions that could be retained on the column, when these ions were allowed to pass through it at a rate of 5 ml/min until the metal ions were first detected in the effluent solution. The saturation of each column containing 1 g of Al-Puf was reached after passing 45–65 ml of 2 mg/100 ml of tested metal ions (Fig. 4). The capacities of the columns of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} were estimated to be 4.16, 2.52 and 2.41 mmol g⁻¹, respectively. This confirms that the dynamic technique is more efficient than the batch method. The capacity sequence was in order Ag^I > Hg^{II} > Pb^{II} which depends on the ionic radius of metal ions. These capacities are quite reasonable in comparison with those reported previously with different chelating resins^{9,10}.

Fig. 4. Breakthrough curve for extraction of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} from aqueous solution : (◆) Ag^I, (■) Hg^{II}, (▲) Pb^{II}.

Effect of eluting agent flow rate : The dependence of the elution of tested metal ions on flow rate was examined by percolating 25 ml of each metal ions (40 μg) through the column at flow rates 5 ml/min. Elution of the Ag^I, Hg^{II} and

Pb^{II} from the column by using 0.1 M HNO₃ was obtained at various flow rates (2, 5 and 7 ml/min). The chromatograms indicate that the tested metal ions could be completely eluted in the first 40–60 ml and the curves were symmetrical with relatively sharp peak. The Al-Puf column performance by the elution chromatogram of metal ions was investigated. The height equivalent to a theoretical plate (HETP) was calculated using Glueckauf (HETP =

$$\frac{L}{N} = \frac{W^2}{16V_R^2}) \text{ and Van Deemeter (HETP} = A + \frac{B}{U} + CU)$$

equations. Where N is number of theoretical plates, V_R is volume of elutes at peak maximum, W is width of the peak, L is length of the foam bed, and A , B and C are constants. The results were shown in Fig. 5. Good column efficiency as indicated by a low value of (HETP), was important if good separations were to be achieved. The HETP values

Fig. 5. Effect of flow rate on the height equivalent theoretical plate of metal ions from aqueous solution using Al-Puf : (◆) Ag^I, (■) Hg^{II}, (▲) Pb^{II}.

were found to be equal 0.38, 0.44 and 0.57 mm at flow rate 3, 4 and 4 ml/min for the eluting of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II}, respectively. The slight increase in values of HETP with the increase of the flow rate occurred in the case of eluting Ag^I ion from the column, so that relatively high flow rate could be applied without any appreciable loss in column performance. The HETP value was also calculated from the breakthrough capacity curve using the equation :

$$N = \frac{VV'}{(V-V')^2} = \frac{L}{\text{HETP}} \quad (3)$$

where V is the volume of effluent at center of S-shaped breakthrough where the concentration is one half the initial concentration, and V' is the volume at which the effluent has a concentration of 0.1587 of the initial concentration. The values of HETP obtained by this equation are 0.36,

0.39 and 0.29 rom for Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} , respectively. While the ideal flow rate (U) can be also calculated ($U = \sqrt{B/C}$). The values of U obtained by this equation are 3.32, 3.82 and 3.91 ml/min, respectively, The values of HETP and U are in a good agreement with those values obtained from the elution curves.

Preconcentration of Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} from aqueous solution : The performance of Al-Puf column in the preconcentration of tested metal ions from different volume (25–1000 ml) was studied. Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} were eluted in less or complete recover (88–100%) from Al-Puf columns (average rsd ~4.98%). The results were summarized in Table 3. These results show that the tested metal ions can be sensitively concentrated from large volumes of dilute aqueous solutions using Al-Puf columns. The preconcentration factor was estimated to be 50 for a volume sample of 20 ml. The detection limit is found to be lower than 4 ng/ml for each element, for a preconcentration time 3–10 min (rsd ~3.46%).

Table 3. Preconcentration factor for Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} using Al-Puf

Volume (ml)	P	Ag^{I}		Hg^{II}		Pb^{II}	
		%E	rsd (%)	%E	rsd (%)	%E	rsd (%)
25	1.25	99		98		100	
50	2.5	99		98		99	
250	12.5	90	5.52	95	4.02	90	5.41
500	25	89		90		90	
1000	50	88		90		89	

Separation of Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} : The dependence of extraction of the tested metal ions on pH values using Al-Puf was examined. From the results obtained, it was observed that Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} ions can be separated from other at appropriated pH value e.g. the selectivity sequence at pH 2 in order $\text{Hg}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ag}^{\text{I}} > \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$. Hence, synthetic mixtures of (50 μg of each ions in 50 ml at pH 2), Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} were passed through the column at flow rate 3 ml/min. The tested metal ions were eluted using 0.01, 0.1 and 2 M HNO_3 . Fig. 6 shows the data obtained. Ag^{I} was first eluted, followed by Pb^{II} and finally Hg^{II} was eluted. This technique selectively allows the determination of each metal ion from the other ions in a mixture.

Collection of metal ions from wastewater : The analytical applicability of the proposed Al-Puf was tested for the collection of metal ions from spiked industrial wastewater from one of the fertilizers and chemicals company. A 100 ml of wastewater was spiked with 1 ml containing 5–10 μg of Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} or Pb^{II} and pH was adjusted to pH ~7. Then the

Fig. 6. Separation of Ag^{I} , Pb^{II} and Hg^{II} from aqueous solution through Al-Puf column by 0.01 M HNO_3 : (◆) Ag^{I} , (■) Pb^{II} , (▲) Hg^{II} .

solutions were passed through Al-Puf columns at flow rate 3–4 ml/min. The metal ions were eluted with 5 ml of 1M HNO_3 . Table 4 shows the results obtained for the tested metal ions in wastewater which are quantitatively recovered using Al-Puf column.

Table 4. Collection of Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} and from wastewater onto Al-Puf

Metal ions	Added (μg)	Found (μg)	Recovery (%E)		
			Ag^{I}	Hg^{II}	Pb^{II}
Ag^{I}	10	8.4	84	0	0
Hg^{II}	10	7	0	70	0
Pb^{II}	10	8.2	0	0	82
$\text{Ag}^{\text{I}} + \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}$	5 + 5	4.1 + 3.0	82	60	0
$\text{Ag}^{\text{I}} + \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$	5 + 5	4.1 + 4.1	82	4.3	82
$\text{Hg}^{\text{II}} + \text{Pb}^{\text{II}}$	5 + 5	3.2 + 4.0	0	64	80

Experimental

Reagents : All reagents used were of A.R. grade. Standard silver solution (1 mg/ml) was prepared by dissolving 1.575 g of AgNO_3 that was previously dried at 110° , in distilled water containing 1 ml of concentrated HNO_3 and diluted the solution to 1 litre with water. For standard mercury solution (1 mg/ml), 1.713 g of $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was dissolved in distilled water containing 1 ml of concentrated HNO_3 , and diluted the solution to 1 litre with water. Standard lead solution (1 mg/ml), 1.598 g of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ was dissolved in water and diluted the solution with water to 1 litre.

Synthesis of Alizarin red S bonded polyurethane foam :

A portion of 5 g of small cubes of white foam ($d = 20 \text{ kg/m}^3$) was washed with water and then with acetone and allowed to dry at RT. To the foam 50 ml of HCl (1 : 1) was added with stirring during 1 h and it was cooled in ice bath.

To the foam was added 10 ml of 0.5 M NaNO₂ solution drop by drop with continuous stirring. Alizarin red S, 0.1 g, was dissolved in 10 ml of 1M NaOH and added to the foam with stirring, and kept for 2 h in the refrigerator. Al-Puf material was washed with 0.1 M HCl distilled water and acetone and dried at RT.

Apparatus :

All spectrophotometric measurements were performed using Spectronic 501, Milton Roy company, and Shimadzu UV-1601, UV-visible spectrophotometer. Glass columns of about 15 cm × 1.5 cm id were employed for the chromatographic separations.

General procedures :

Sorption investigations : Separations of silver, lead and mercury ions were carried out by a batch technique at RT except otherwise specified. A 0.2 g portion of the Al-Puf was mixed with 25 ml aliquot of tested metal ion solution (40 µg/25 ml) in a shaker thermostated to the desired temperature and adjusted to a desired shaking speed. After fixed intervals aliquots of solution were withdrawn and the concentration of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} ions were determined spectrophotometrically. The following equations have been used to calculate the distribution coefficients (K_d), percentage uptake (%E) and batch capacities (Q_c),

$$K_d = \frac{C_0 - C}{C} \times \frac{V}{M} \quad (4)$$

$$\%E = \frac{C_0 - C}{C} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

$$Q_c = \frac{\%E}{100} \times C_0 \times \frac{V}{M} \quad (6)$$

where C_0 and C are the initial and final concentrations of sorbed metal ions in solution, respectively. V is the volume of solution and M is the mass of the Al-Puf.

Chromatographic separations : To study the preconcentration, the breakthrough capacities, the chromatographic behaviour, and separation of the metal ion, a compact column of 15 cm × 1.5 cm id was packed with 1 g of the Al-Puf. Solutions were passed through the column at flow rate of 3 ml/min.

Conclusion :

The present work deals with the preparation of new chelating resin by coupling of polyurethane foam with Alizarin red S. This new polymeric extractor was used to collect, preconcentrate, and remove of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} from wastewater. Al-Puf was found denser than the white

Table 5. Optimum conditions for separation of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} onto Al-puf

Parameter	Ag ^I	Hg ^{II}	Pb ^{II}
pH	9	1-6	4-6
Flow rate (ml/min)	4	3	4
Eluting agent (M HNO ₃)	0.1	0.01	2
Loading half time ($t_{1/2}$) min.	3.28	1.55	3.35
Separation capacities (mmol/g)	3.14	1.75	1.50
(dynamic tech.)	4.16	2.52	2.41
% Average recovery (batch tech.)	85	78	82
(dynamic tech.)	93	94.2	93.6
Relative standard deviation (%)	5.52	4.02	5.41

foam due to the additional bonds between the reagent and the other groups in foam matrix. From our study Al-Puf has ability to separate Ag^I, Hg^{II} or Pb^{II} from other at appropriated pH value. Also, the tested metal ions can be sensitively preconcentrated from large volumes of dilute aqueous solutions. The optimum conditions for separation and preconcentration of Ag^I, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II} onto Al-Puf were summarized in Table 5.

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